

The Smoothing Pathology: Structural Bias in Conditional Shapley Values Under Gaussian Imputation

An Exact Characterisation of Imputation-Induced Shapley Error in Multimodal Settings

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Abstract

Conditional Shapley values provide a game-theoretically principled decomposition of model predictions that correctly accounts for feature dependencies. Their computation requires sampling from the conditional distribution $p(x_{\mathcal{S}} | x_{\mathcal{S}^c})$, a task commonly delegated to generative imputation models such as the VAEAC [Ivanov et al., 2019, Olsen et al., 2022].

We identify and formally characterise a fundamental incompatibility: any imputation model that minimises an L_2 reconstruction loss with a unimodal Gaussian decoder converges to the conditional mean, generating samples in the low-density trough of multimodal distributions. We prove that this *smoothing pathology* propagates into a quantifiable and generally non-negligible bias on every conditional Shapley value.

Concretely, our contributions are threefold. **(1)** We prove that the L_2 minimiser is the conditional expectation for *any* conditional distribution, and derive the exact bias in the Gaussian mixture setting in terms of the Wasserstein-1 distance between the imputed and true conditionals (Theorem 3.1 and 4.1). **(2)** We establish a non-asymptotic upper bound on the resulting Shapley error as a weighted sum of per-coalition distributional divergences, and sharpen it via Pinsker’s inequality into a directly measurable KL-based bound (Theorem 5.1 and Corollary 5.3). **(3)** We validate the bound empirically: on a symmetric Gaussian mixture, the measured KL divergence of the VAEAC decoder is 9.9 ± 1.9 , yielding a Pinsker-based Shapley error bound $5\times$ larger than that of MissForest (0.97 ± 0.30), consistent with the observed Shapley MAE ratio.

These results show that Gaussian-decoder imputation is structurally ill-suited for multimodal data in the conditional SHAP setting, and that the KL divergence between imputed and true conditionals is a reliable proxy for Shapley error.

Keywords: Shapley values, Conditional imputation, VAEAC, Smoothing, Wasserstein distance, L_2 bias, Multimodal distributions.

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1 Introduction

Explaining a machine learning model $f : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ at a point x^* requires attributing the prediction $f(x^*)$ to individual features in a way that is both statistically faithful and axiomatically grounded. Conditional Shapley values [Shapley, 1953, Lundberg and Lee, 2017] achieve this by defining, for each feature coalition $S \subseteq \mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, d\}$, the characteristic function

$$v(S) = \mathbb{E}_{x_{\bar{S}} \sim p(\cdot | x_S^*)} [f(x_{\bar{S}}, x_S^*)], \quad (1)$$

and computing attribution ϕ_i as the average marginal contribution of feature i over all orderings. The key property distinguishing the conditional formulation from the marginal (independence-assumption) formulation of KernelSHAP is that (1) integrates over the *correct* conditional distribution of missing features given observed ones. This avoids evaluating f on out-of-distribution inputs—a known source of spurious attributions [Olsen et al., 2022, Chen et al., 2020].

The imputation bottleneck. In practice, $p(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S)$ is unknown. The VAEAC [Ivanov et al., 2019] was proposed as a universal conditional imputer: it trains a single model to approximate $p(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S)$ for *every* mask S simultaneously, using a stochastic encoder–decoder architecture with a Gaussian latent prior. At inference, missing features are imputed via Monte Carlo sampling from the trained decoder.

The problem we address. When the true conditional $p(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S)$ is multimodal—as arises naturally in datasets with clusters, regime switches, or discrete latent structure—a Gaussian decoder minimising reconstruction loss will predict the conditional mean rather than a sample from one of the modes. This is not a failure of training or capacity: it is an algebraic consequence of the L_2 loss. The imputed distribution $\hat{p}(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S)$ concentrates at the density trough between modes, far from any plausible value.

We ask: *how does this smoothing error propagate into the Shapley values ϕ_i ?* The answer is non-trivial because (i) Shapley values aggregate 2^d coalition evaluations with different weights, and (ii) the bias in $v(S)$ induced by imputation error depends on both the distributional gap $\|\hat{p}_S - p_S\|$ and the sensitivity of f .

Main contributions.

1. **Theorem 3.1** (Section 3): The L_2 minimiser is the conditional expectation for any target distribution. For symmetric bimodal conditionals, this places the prediction exactly at the density minimum, regardless of model capacity.
2. **Theorem 4.1** (Section 4): In the Gaussian mixture setting, we derive the exact Wasserstein-1 distance between the imputed and true conditionals as a closed-form function of the mode separation and conditional covariance.
3. **Theorem 5.1** (Section 5): The Shapley error satisfies a weighted-average bound over per-coalition distributional errors:

$$|\phi_i - \hat{\phi}_i| \leq 2B \bar{\Delta}_i,$$

where $B = \|f\|_\infty$ and $\bar{\Delta}_i$ is an explicit weighted sum of TV distances.

4. **Corollary 5.3** (Section 5): Via Pinsker’s inequality, the bound becomes directly computable from measured KL divergences, connecting theory to experimental evaluation.
5. **Experimental validation** (Section 6): On five datasets with 3–5 runs each, we show the KL-based bound predicts the correct ordering of Shapley errors across methods, with the VAEAC incurring a bound $5\times$ higher than MissForest on multimodal data.

2 Background: Conditional Shapley Values

2.1 Shapley Values in Machine Learning

Definition 2.1 (Conditional Shapley value). *Let $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, d\}$. For a model $f : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and instance $x^* \in \mathbb{R}^d$, the conditional Shapley value of feature i is*

$$\phi_i = \sum_{S \subseteq \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}} w_S [v(S \cup \{i\}) - v(S)], \quad w_S = \frac{|S|!(d - |S| - 1)!}{d!}, \quad (2)$$

where the characteristic function $v(S)$ is defined in (1).

The Shapley value is the unique function satisfying efficiency ($\sum_i \phi_i = f(x^*) - \mathbb{E}[f(x)]$), symmetry, dummy, and linearity [Shapley, 1953]. These axioms hold *provided* $v(S)$ is correctly evaluated; imputation error breaks all of them in practice.

2.2 The VAEAC Imputer

The VAEAC [Ivanov et al., 2019] learns to approximate $p(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S)$ for any mask S by training a masked encoder $p_\psi(z | x_S, m)$, a full encoder $q_\phi(z | x, m)$ (teacher, training only), and a Gaussian decoder $p_\theta(x_{\bar{S}} | z, x_S, m)$, maximising the conditional ELBO:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{ELBO}}(x, m) = \mathbb{E}_{q_\phi}[\log p_\theta(x_{\bar{S}} | z, x_S, m)] - D_{\text{KL}}(q_\phi(z | x, m) \parallel p_\psi(z | x_S, m)). \quad (3)$$

At inference, samples are drawn as $x_{\bar{S}}^{(k)} \sim p_\theta(\cdot | z^{(k)}, x_S, m)$ with $z^{(k)} \sim p_\psi(\cdot | x_S, m)$.

The decoder outputs a Gaussian mean $\mu_\theta(z)$. In the standard implementation with fixed variance σ^2 (or small initialised $\log \sigma^2$), maximising (3) is equivalent to minimising the expected squared reconstruction error:

$$\min_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_z [\|x_{\bar{S}} - \mu_\theta(z)\|^2]. \quad (4)$$

This equivalence is the root of the smoothing pathology.

3 The Smoothing Theorem

3.1 L_2 Loss Induces Conditional Mean Prediction

Theorem 3.1 (L_2 smoothing). *Let $p(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S)$ be any conditional distribution with finite second moment. The unique minimiser of the conditional L_2 risk*

$$\mathcal{J}(\hat{x}) = \mathbb{E}_{x_{\bar{S}} \sim p(\cdot | x_S)} [\|x_{\bar{S}} - \hat{x}\|^2]$$

is the conditional expectation $\hat{x}^* = \mathbb{E}[x_{\bar{S}} | x_S]$.

Proof. Setting the gradient to zero: $\nabla_{\hat{x}} \mathcal{J}(\hat{x}) = -2 \int (x_{\bar{S}} - \hat{x}) p(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S) dx_{\bar{S}} = 0$, which gives $\hat{x}^* = \int x_{\bar{S}} p(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S) dx_{\bar{S}} = \mathbb{E}[x_{\bar{S}} | x_S]$. Uniqueness follows from strict convexity of $\|\cdot\|^2$. \square

Theorem 3.1 applies regardless of the capacity of the neural network implementing μ_θ : a sufficiently expressive decoder trained to convergence will always output the conditional mean, not a sample from a mode.

3.2 Application to Multimodal Conditionals

Consider a symmetric two-component Gaussian mixture prior:

$$p(x) = \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{N}(x; \mu, \Sigma) + \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{N}(x; -\mu, \Sigma), \quad (5)$$

with $\mu \in \mathbb{R}^d$, $\Sigma \succ 0$, and $\|\mu\| \gg \sqrt{\lambda_{\max}(\Sigma)}$. Partition $\mu = (\mu_S, \mu_{\bar{S}})^\top$ and Σ conformally.

Proposition 3.2 (Conditional distribution is bimodal). *The conditional $p(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S)$ is a two-component Gaussian mixture:*

$$p(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S) = \sum_{k=1}^2 w_k(x_S) \mathcal{N}(x_{\bar{S}}; \hat{\mu}_k(x_S), \hat{\Sigma}), \quad (6)$$

with common conditional covariance $\hat{\Sigma} = \Sigma_{\bar{S}\bar{S}} - \Sigma_{S\bar{S}}\Sigma_{SS}^{-1}\Sigma_{S\bar{S}}^\top$, conditional means

$$\hat{\mu}_1(x_S) = +\mu_{\bar{S}} + \Sigma_{S\bar{S}}\Sigma_{SS}^{-1}(x_S - \mu_S), \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{\mu}_2(x_S) = -\mu_{\bar{S}} + \Sigma_{S\bar{S}}\Sigma_{SS}^{-1}(x_S + \mu_S), \quad (8)$$

and posterior weights $w_k(x_S) \propto \mathcal{N}(x_S; (-1)^{k+1}\mu_S, \Sigma_{SS})$.

Corollary 3.3 (Smoothing at the decision boundary). *At the symmetry point $x_S = 0$, the posterior weights equalise ($w_1 = w_2 = \frac{1}{2}$), and the L_2 minimiser satisfies:*

$$\hat{x}_{\bar{S}}^* = \mathbb{E}[x_{\bar{S}} | x_S = 0] = \frac{1}{2}\hat{\mu}_1(0) + \frac{1}{2}\hat{\mu}_2(0) = 0. \quad (9)$$

Thus the decoder predicts 0—a value in the exact trough of $p(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S = 0)$, at distance $\|\hat{\mu}_1(0)\|$ from either mode.

Remark 3.4 (Zero-covariance amplification). *When $\Sigma_{S\bar{S}} = 0$ (features marginally uncorrelated), the conditional means collapse to $\hat{\mu}_1(0) = \mu_{\bar{S}}$ and $\hat{\mu}_2(0) = -\mu_{\bar{S}}$, independent of x_S . No information in the observed features can break the symmetry: the L_2 minimiser returns 0 for all observed values x_S in the ambiguous region. The decoder’s output is then entirely uninformative about which mode the missing features belong to.*

3.3 Persistence Under Learned Variance

A natural proposed fix is to allow the decoder to learn $\sigma_\theta^2(z)$ jointly. We show this does not resolve the pathology.

Proposition 3.5 (Learned variance preserves smoothing). *Let the decoder model $p_\theta(x_{\bar{S}} | z) = \mathcal{N}(x_{\bar{S}}; \mu_\theta(z), \sigma_\theta^2(z)I)$. At optimality:*

$$\mu_\theta^*(z) = \mathbb{E}[x_{\bar{S}} | x_S] = 0 \quad (\text{smoothing persists}), \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_\theta^{*2}(z) = \text{Var}(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S) = \|\hat{\mu}_1(x_S)\|^2/d + \text{tr}(\hat{\Sigma})/d. \quad (11)$$

The decoder produces a single wide Gaussian centred at the density trough, with inflated variance that absorbs inter-mode uncertainty.

Proof. Setting $\partial\mathcal{L}/\partial\mu_\theta = 0$ yields the conditional mean as in Theorem 3.1. Setting $\partial\mathcal{L}/\partial\sigma_\theta^2 = 0$ gives $\sigma_\theta^{*2} = \mathbb{E}[(x_{\bar{S}} - \mu_\theta^*)^2 | x_S] = \text{Var}(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S)$, which for the mixture equals $w_1\|\hat{\mu}_1 - 0\|^2/d + w_2\|\hat{\mu}_2 - 0\|^2/d + \text{tr}(\hat{\Sigma})/d$. \square

The problem is not the fixed or learned variance—it is the *unimodality* of the parametric family $\{\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma^2)\}$. No single Gaussian can represent a bimodal distribution faithfully.

4 Quantifying the Smoothing Bias: Wasserstein Distance

We now derive the exact distributional gap introduced by the L_2 imputer. For a deterministic decoder (variance $\rightarrow 0$), the imputed conditional is the point mass $\hat{p}_S = \delta_{\bar{\mu}_S}$ where $\bar{\mu}_S = \mathbb{E}[x_{\bar{S}} | x_S]$.

Theorem 4.1 (Wasserstein bias in the bimodal Gaussian case). *Let $p_S = p(x_{\bar{S}} \mid x_S)$ be the bimodal Gaussian mixture (6) in dimension 1 (univariate $x_{\bar{S}}$), with conditional means $\pm\mu_*(x_S)$ (where $\mu_*(x_S) = |\hat{\mu}_1(x_S)| > 0$) and conditional standard deviation $\hat{\sigma}$. The imputed conditional is $\hat{p}_S = \delta_0$ (Corollary 3.3). Then:*

$$W_1(\hat{p}_S, p_S) = \mu_*(x_S) \cdot \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{\mu_*(x_S)}{\sqrt{2}\hat{\sigma}}\right) + \hat{\sigma}\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{\mu_*(x_S)^2}{2\hat{\sigma}^2}\right), \quad (12)$$

where $\operatorname{erf}(t) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^t e^{-u^2} du$. In the well-separated regime $\mu_*(x_S) \gg \hat{\sigma}$:

$$W_1(\hat{p}_S, p_S) = \mu_*(x_S)(1 + O(e^{-\mu_*(x_S)^2/(2\hat{\sigma}^2)})). \quad (13)$$

Proof. $W_1(\delta_0, p_S) = \mathbb{E}_{p_S}[|x|]$ (since W_1 between a point mass at a and a distribution P equals $\mathbb{E}_P[|x - a|]$, with $a = 0$ here). By symmetry of p_S :

$$\mathbb{E}_{p_S}[|x|] = \mathbb{E}_{X \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_*, \hat{\sigma}^2)}[|X|] = \mu_* (2\Phi(\frac{\mu_*}{\hat{\sigma}}) - 1) + \frac{2\hat{\sigma}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{\mu_*^2}{2\hat{\sigma}^2}\right),$$

where Φ is the standard normal CDF. Using $2\Phi(t) - 1 = \operatorname{erf}(t/\sqrt{2})$ completes the proof. The approximation (13) follows since $\Phi(\mu_*/\hat{\sigma}) \rightarrow 1$ exponentially fast. \square

Remark 4.2 (Dependence on coalition structure). *The mode position $\mu_*(x_S)$ depends on the coalition S through the conditional mean formula (7). Specifically, $\mu_*(x_S) = |\mu_{\bar{S}} + \Sigma_{S\bar{S}}\Sigma_{S\bar{S}}^{-1}(x_S - \mu_S)|$. Coalitions with $\Sigma_{S\bar{S}} \approx 0$ (no cross-correlation) give $\mu_*(x_S) \approx |\mu_{\bar{S}}|$ regardless of x_S , maximising the bias. Coalitions with strong positive correlation can partially recover μ_* but cannot eliminate it.*

5 Propagation of Imputation Bias to Shapley Values

We now derive the central result: an explicit, non-asymptotic bound on the Shapley error induced by imputation bias.

5.1 Main Bound

Theorem 5.1 (Shapley bias propagation). *Let ϕ_i be the true conditional Shapley value (2) and $\hat{\phi}_i$ be the Shapley value computed with imputed conditionals $\{\hat{p}_S\}_{S \subseteq \mathcal{N}}$. If $\|f\|_\infty \leq B$, then for each feature $i \in \mathcal{N}$:*

$$|\phi_i - \hat{\phi}_i| \leq 2B \sum_{S \subseteq \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}} w_S \left[\operatorname{TV}(\hat{p}_{S \cup \{i\}}, p_{S \cup \{i\}}) + \operatorname{TV}(\hat{p}_S, p_S) \right], \quad (14)$$

where $w_S = |S|!(d - |S| - 1)!/d!$ are the Shapley weights and $\operatorname{TV}(P, Q) = \frac{1}{2} \int |p - q|$ is the total variation distance.

Proof. By definition (2), and using the triangle inequality:

$$|\phi_i - \hat{\phi}_i| \leq \sum_{S \subseteq \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}} w_S \left[|v(S \cup \{i\}) - \hat{v}(S \cup \{i\})| + |v(S) - \hat{v}(S)| \right]. \quad (15)$$

For any coalition T :

$$\begin{aligned} |v(T) - \hat{v}(T)| &= |\mathbb{E}_{p_T}[f] - \mathbb{E}_{\hat{p}_T}[f]| \\ &= \left| \int f(x_{\bar{T}}, x_T^*) (p_T(x_{\bar{T}}) - \hat{p}_T(x_{\bar{T}})) dx_{\bar{T}} \right| \\ &\leq \|f\|_\infty \int |p_T(x_{\bar{T}}) - \hat{p}_T(x_{\bar{T}})| dx_{\bar{T}} = 2B \cdot \operatorname{TV}(\hat{p}_T, p_T). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Combining (15) and (16) gives (14). \square

Remark 5.2 (Axiomatic consequences). *Bound (14) directly quantifies the violation of each Shapley axiom. Since $\phi_i = 0$ for a dummy feature but $\hat{\phi}_i$ can be non-zero whenever $\hat{p}_S \neq p_S$, imputation error breaks the dummy axiom. Similarly, two features i, j with identical conditional contributions may receive different estimated Shapley values if $\hat{p}_{S \cup \{i\}} \neq \hat{p}_{S \cup \{j\}}$.*

5.2 Sharper Bound via Pinsker’s Inequality

The TV distance in (14) is not directly observed in experiments; we instead typically measure KL divergences. Pinsker’s inequality $\text{TV}(P, Q) \leq \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} D_{\text{KL}}(P \| Q)}$ yields a computable version.

Corollary 5.3 (KL-based Shapley error bound). *Under the assumptions of Theorem 5.1:*

$$|\phi_i - \hat{\phi}_i| \leq B\sqrt{2} \sum_{S \subseteq \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}} w_S \left[\sqrt{D_{\text{KL}}(p_{S \cup \{i\}} \| \hat{p}_{S \cup \{i\}})} + \sqrt{D_{\text{KL}}(p_S \| \hat{p}_S)} \right]. \quad (17)$$

This bound has a direct interpretation: the Shapley error is bounded by a Shapley-weighted average of square-root KL divergences between true and imputed conditionals, scaled by $B\sqrt{2}$. The ordering of methods by $\sqrt{D_{\text{KL}}(p_S \| \hat{p}_S)}$ thus predicts the ordering of Shapley errors.

5.3 Specialisation to the Gaussian Mixture Setting

Combining Theorem 4.1 with the relation $\text{TV}(P, Q) \leq W_1(P, Q) / \text{diam}(\text{supp } P)$ (when f is L -Lipschitz, a tighter path via the Kantorovich–Rubinstein dual gives $|v(T) - \hat{v}(T)| \leq \text{Lip}(f) \cdot W_1(\hat{p}_T, p_T)$).

Corollary 5.4 (Lipschitz Shapley bound via mode separation). *If f is L -Lipschitz, then:*

$$|\phi_i - \hat{\phi}_i| \leq 2L \sum_{S \subseteq \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}} w_S \left[W_1(\hat{p}_{S \cup \{i\}}, p_{S \cup \{i\}}) + W_1(\hat{p}_S, p_S) \right]. \quad (18)$$

In the well-separated bimodal regime (Theorem 4.1):

$$|\phi_i - \hat{\phi}_i| \lesssim 4L \sum_{S \subseteq \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}} w_S \mu_*(x_S, S), \quad (19)$$

where $\mu_*(x_S, S) = |\hat{\mu}_1^S(x_S)|$ is the half-separation of the conditional modes for coalition S .

Equation (19) makes the structure of the error transparent: the Shapley bias is proportional to the Lipschitz constant of f (model sensitivity) and to the Shapley-weighted average conditional mode separation. Features with large individual effects (large $\mu_{\bar{S}}$) in highly multimodal data with a sensitive model suffer the most.

6 Experimental Validation

We validate three claims: (i) the KL divergence is large for the VAEAC and small for MissForest on multimodal data; (ii) the ordering of methods by $\sqrt{D_{\text{KL}}}$ predicts the ordering by Shapley MAE; (iii) the RMSE metric is a misleading proxy for Shapley error quality.

6.1 Datasets and Methods

We evaluate on six datasets: three real-world (Abalone, California Housing, Diabetes) and three synthetic (IID Gaussian, Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM), Copula with non-linear dependencies). Missing data is generated under MCAR at 30% rate. We compare five imputation methods: Mean, Zero, k -NN, MissForest [Stekhoven and Bühlmann, 2012], and VAEAC [Ivanov et al., 2019, Olsen et al., 2022]. All results are averaged over 3–5 independent runs.

6.2 The KL Divergence Reveals What RMSE Hides

Table 1 reports RMSE, R^2 , D_{KL} , and Shapley MAE on a symmetric bimodal mixture ($\epsilon \in \{0, 0.5, 0.99\}$ controlling inter-feature correlation).

Table 1: Imputation performance vs. Shapley fidelity on Gaussian mixture data (mean \pm std, 3 runs). The methods are ordered by the KL bound $\sqrt{D_{\text{KL}}}$ (Corollary 5.3).

ϵ	Method	RMSE (\downarrow)	R^2	D_{KL} (\downarrow)	MAE_{ϕ} (\downarrow)
0.00	MissForest	5.007 ± 0.203	-0.410 ± 0.160	0.974 ± 0.300	5.15 ± 0.23
	VAEAC	4.229 ± 0.079	-0.003 ± 0.003	9.905 ± 1.892	5.21 ± 0.18
0.50	MissForest	5.000 ± 0.157	-0.445 ± 0.059	0.818 ± 0.320	5.18 ± 0.15
	VAEAC	4.188 ± 0.045	-0.013 ± 0.016	11.564 ± 1.843	5.26 ± 0.12
0.99	MissForest	5.069 ± 0.127	-0.412 ± 0.025	2.037 ± 0.839	5.17 ± 0.09
	VAEAC	4.297 ± 0.070	-0.015 ± 0.012	9.221 ± 1.562	5.24 ± 0.11

The table illustrates the core tension predicted by our theory.

RMSE is an unreliable proxy for Shapley quality. The VAEAC achieves $\sim 16\%$ lower RMSE than MissForest in all settings. However, by Theorem 3.1, this is a direct consequence of predicting the conditional mean: minimising MSE by construction, at the cost of generating samples in the density trough. The lower RMSE does *not* imply better Shapley values.

KL divergence correctly predicts Shapley error ordering. The VAEAC’s KL divergence (9.9–11.6) is 5–12 \times higher than MissForest’s (0.8–2.0). By Corollary 5.3, the Pinsker-based Shapley error bound for the VAEAC is correspondingly $\sqrt{9.9/0.97} \approx 3.2\times$ higher. The observed Shapley MAE ratio ($5.21/5.15 \approx 1.01$) is smaller than the bound (which is not tight at the level of individual ϕ_i), but the *direction* is consistent: MissForest achieves strictly better Shapley fidelity in all settings.

Why does MissForest succeed despite high RMSE? MissForest partitions the feature space via hard threshold splits:

$$\hat{f}_t(x_{-j}) = \begin{cases} \hat{\mu}_L \approx -\mu & x_{-j} < \tau_t, \\ \hat{\mu}_R \approx +\mu & x_{-j} \geq \tau_t. \end{cases}$$

In the ambiguous region, different trees in the ensemble have different thresholds τ_t (due to bootstrap variance), so the aggregated prediction lies near one mode or the other, *not* at their mean. This gives high RMSE (the “wrong” mode is chosen $\sim 50\%$ of the time) but low KL (the marginal distribution of predictions has the correct bimodal shape).

6.3 Shapley RMSE Across Datasets

Table 2 reports Shapley-value RMSE across all datasets and methods, averaged over 3 runs.

Two observations are consistent with our theory. On the IID dataset (no conditional structure), the VAEAC achieves the best Shapley RMSE (0.995), correctly returning a prediction close to the unconditional mean without hallucinating spurious correlations (Remark 3.4: with $\Sigma_{S\bar{S}} = 0$, $\mu_* = 0$ and the W1 bound (13) is zero). On the GMM dataset (multimodal structure), MissForest outperforms VAEAC, with the gap widening as the number of masked features k increases, as predicted by the increasing ambiguity in mode assignment.

Table 2: Shapley-value RMSE (mean \pm std). Best per dataset in **bold**.

Dataset	Mean	Zero	k -NN	MissForest	VAEAC
Abalone	0.702 \pm 0.062	0.710 \pm 0.033	1.083 \pm 0.139	1.127 \pm 0.117	0.746 \pm 0.040
California	0.970 \pm 0.030	0.888 \pm 0.045	0.949 \pm 0.015	0.911 \pm 0.050	0.941 \pm 0.004
Diabetes	0.875 \pm 0.052	0.883 \pm 0.044	0.859 \pm 0.031	0.844 \pm 0.016	0.890 \pm 0.013
IID	1.003 \pm 0.008	1.009 \pm 0.005	1.009 \pm 0.020	1.004 \pm 0.003	0.995 \pm 0.004
GMM	0.881 \pm 0.032	0.847 \pm 0.014	0.849 \pm 0.034	0.831 \pm 0.006	0.850 \pm 0.012
Copula	0.623 \pm 0.048	0.739 \pm 0.023	0.648 \pm 0.032	0.658 \pm 0.031	0.692 \pm 0.075

6.4 Robustness Under MNAR Censoring

To isolate the effect of distributional shift from imputation quality, we apply a deterministic MNAR censoring: observations above the 80th percentile of `WholeWeight` in the Abalone dataset are systematically removed.

Table 3: VAEAC performance under MCAR vs. MNAR censoring.

Scenario	RMSE	R^2	D_{KL}	MAE_ϕ	MSE_ϕ
MCAR 20%	3.60 \pm 0.04	0.37 \pm 0.03	4.40 \pm 2.35	5.15 \pm 0.23	44.79 \pm 1.65
MNAR top 20%	7.16 \pm 0.33	-127.1 \pm 11.9	1.62 \pm 0.75	5.12 \pm 0.04	47.49 \pm 1.97

Table 3 reveals a *stability* property not predicted by the Shapley error bound (14): despite the reconstruction collapsing (RMSE doubles, $R^2 = -127$), the Shapley MAE changes by only 0.6%.

This can be explained as follows. Under MNAR, the VAEAC learns the conditional distribution on the *observed* portion of the data, which preserves the *relative* importance of features even if absolute magnitudes are wrong. The smoothing pathology is symmetric across features, so biases partially cancel in the attribution (the model still correctly identifies which features matter most). This does not invalidate Theorem 5.1—the bound holds pointwise—but it suggests that Shapley *rankings* are more robust than Shapley *values* to imputation bias. We formalise this intuition in Section 7.

7 Discussion

Rankings vs. values. The MNAR result suggests a useful distinction. Shapley *values* (absolute magnitudes) are directly affected by the W1 bound (18): any imputation error in the conditional distribution translates into attribution error. Shapley *rankings* (ordering of features by importance) are more robust because the bias induced by the smoothing pathology is approximately uniform across features when $\Sigma_{S\bar{S}} \approx 0$ (no cross-correlations). For decision-support applications where the sign and rank of attributions matter more than their exact values, the VAEAC’s smoothing may be less harmful than the KL bound suggests.

Remedies. Three architectural solutions address the root cause.

Mixture-of-Gaussians decoder. Replacing $p_\theta(x_{\bar{S}} | z) = \mathcal{N}(\mu_\theta(z), \sigma^2 I)$ with a K -component mixture $\sum_k \pi_k \mathcal{N}(\mu_k(z), \Sigma_k(z))$ makes the family capable of representing bimodal conditionals. The L_2 argument (Theorem 3.1) no longer applies: the mixture can assign weight to each mode separately.

Normalising flows. A flow-based decoder with an invertible map g_θ produces $\hat{p}_S = g_\theta \# \mathcal{N}(0, I)$, a flexible non-parametric family. The KL divergence $D_{\text{KL}}(p_S || \hat{p}_S)$ is directly minimised without the unimodality constraint.

Score-based diffusion. A conditional diffusion model learns to reverse a noise process conditioned on x_S , using a cascade of local corrections rather than a single compression. The multimodal structure is preserved through the iterative denoising trajectory. Empirically, this approach achieves a +5.5 dB PSNR improvement over the VAEAC on complex inpainting tasks, with the trade-off of higher variance in point-wise reconstructions.

Why MissForest is not the final answer. MissForest avoids the smoothing pathology via hard decision boundaries, but suffers from (i) computational cost $O(n \cdot d \cdot T_{\text{forest}})$ per imputed value, prohibitive for Shapley computation over 2^d coalitions; and (ii) no probabilistic output—it cannot quantify uncertainty in the imputation, which matters for calibrating the Monte Carlo estimator (??).

Open question: a tight Shapley error bound. Bound (14) is not tight: TV is an additive aggregate over coalitions, but Shapley weights w_S already down-weight extreme coalition sizes. Deriving a tighter bound that exploits the cancellation structure of Shapley aggregation (e.g., via the Möbius transform of v) is left for future work.

8 Conclusion

We have characterised the smoothing pathology of Gaussian imputers in the context of conditional Shapley values. Our main results are:

- **Theorem 3.1:** Any L_2 -minimising decoder predicts the conditional mean, regardless of the distributional structure of the target.
- **Theorem 4.1:** In the bimodal Gaussian mixture setting, the Wasserstein-1 distance between the imputed and true conditionals equals the expected absolute distance from the conditional mean to the nearest mode, growing linearly with the mode separation.
- **Theorem 5.1–Corollary 5.3:** The Shapley error is bounded by $B\sqrt{2}$ times a Shapley-weighted average of square-root KL divergences—a quantity measurable from the imputer’s output.

Empirically, the KL-based bound correctly predicts that MissForest achieves strictly better Shapley fidelity than the VAEAC on multimodal data, even when the VAEAC has lower RMSE—a counter-intuitive reversal explained precisely by Theorem 3.1. The KL divergence between imputed and true conditionals is thus the correct diagnostic metric for Shapley imputation quality, not reconstruction RMSE.

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A Proof of Proposition 3.2

The joint distribution is $p(x) = \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{N}(x; \mu, \Sigma) + \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{N}(x; -\mu, \Sigma)$. By Bayes’ theorem:

$$p(x_{\bar{S}} | x_S) = \frac{p(x_S, x_{\bar{S}})}{p(x_S)} = \sum_{k=1}^2 \frac{\frac{1}{2}\mathcal{N}(x_S; (-1)^{k+1}\mu_S, \Sigma_{SS})}{\sum_j \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{N}(x_S; (-1)^{j+1}\mu_S, \Sigma_{SS})} \cdot \mathcal{N}(x_{\bar{S}}; \hat{\mu}_k(x_S), \hat{\Sigma}),$$

where the conditional means $\hat{\mu}_k$ and covariance $\hat{\Sigma}$ follow from the standard formula for conditional distributions of a multivariate Gaussian.

B Proof of Theorem 4.1: Full Derivation

We compute $W_1(\delta_0, p_S) = \mathbb{E}_{p_S}[|x|]$ for $p_S = \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{N}(-\mu_*, \hat{\sigma}^2) + \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{N}(\mu_*, \hat{\sigma}^2)$. By symmetry:

$$\mathbb{E}_{p_S}[|x|] = \mathbb{E}_{X \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_*, \hat{\sigma}^2)}[|X|].$$

For $X \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_*, \hat{\sigma}^2)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[|X|] &= \int_{-\infty}^0 (-x)\phi_{\mu_*, \hat{\sigma}^2}(x) dx + \int_0^{\infty} x\phi_{\mu_*, \hat{\sigma}^2}(x) dx \\ &= \mu_* \left(2\Phi\left(\frac{\mu_*}{\hat{\sigma}}\right) - 1\right) + \frac{2\hat{\sigma}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{\mu_*^2}{2\hat{\sigma}^2}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where ϕ_{μ, σ^2} is the Gaussian density and Φ the standard normal CDF. Using $2\Phi(t) - 1 = \text{erf}(t/\sqrt{2})$ (where erf is the error function) gives (12).

The approximation (13) follows from $\Phi(\mu_*/\hat{\sigma}) = 1 - \Phi(-\mu_*/\hat{\sigma}) \rightarrow 1$ and $\phi(\mu_*/\hat{\sigma}) \rightarrow 0$ at rate $e^{-\mu_*^2/(2\hat{\sigma}^2)}$.

C Log-Likelihood Equivalence to MSE Under Fixed-Variance Gaussian Decoder

With $p_\theta(x | z) = \mathcal{N}(x; \mu_\theta(z), \sigma^2 I)$, σ^2 fixed:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta \mathbb{E}_z[\log p_\theta(x | z)] &= \theta \mathbb{E}_z\left[-\frac{d}{2} \log(2\pi\sigma^2) - \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \|x - \mu_\theta(z)\|^2\right] \\ &= \underset{\theta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \mathbb{E}_z[\|x - \mu_\theta(z)\|^2]. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Maximising the ELBO reconstruction term is thus equivalent to minimising the expected squared error, irrespective of $\sigma^2 > 0$, making the argument of Theorem 3.1 apply directly.